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Dissociation of impulsivity and aggression in mice deficient for the ADHD risk gene *Adgrl3*: evidence for dopamine transporter dysregulation

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Abstract

Adhesion G protein-coupled receptor L3 (ADGRL3, LPHN3) has putative roles in neuronal migration and synapse function. Various polymorphisms in *ADGRL3* have been linked with an increased risk of attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD). In this study, we examined the characteristics of *Adgrl3*-deficient mice in multiple behavioural domains related to ADHD: locomotive activity, impulsivity, gait, visuospatial and recognition memory, sociability, anxiety-like behaviour and aggression. Additionally, we investigated the effect of *Adgrl3*-depletion at the transcriptomic level by RNA-sequencing three ADHD-relevant brain regions: prefrontal cortex (PFC), hippocampus and striatum.

Adgrl3^{-/-} mice show increased locomotive activity across all tests and subtle gait abnormalities. These mice also show impairments across spatial memory and learning domains, alongside increased levels of impulsivity and sociability with decreased aggression. However, these alterations were absent in *Adgrl3*^{+/-} mice. Across all brain regions tested, the numbers of genes found to exhibit differential expression was relatively small, indicating a specific pathway of action, rather than a broad neurobiological perturbation. Gene-set analysis of differential expression in the PFC detected a number of ADHD-relevant pathways including dopaminergic synapses as well as cocaine and amphetamine addiction. The *Slc6a3* gene coding for the dopamine transporter was the most dysregulated gene in the PFC. Unexpectedly, several neurohormone/peptides which are typically only expressed in the hypothalamus were found to be dysregulated in the striatum. Our study further validates *Adgrl3* constitutive knockout mice as an experimental model of ADHD while providing neuroanatomical targets for future studies involving *ADGRL3* modified models.

Introduction

Attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is defined as a clinically heterogeneous neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by inattention, hyperactivity and increased impulsivity/emotionality (Association, 2013). Although not forming part of the diagnostic criteria, individuals with ADHD often display learning deficits and mood instability (Haavik et al., 2010; Tillman et al., 2009) as well as a variety of motor problems including gait alterations (Gillberg, 2003; Karatekin et al., 2003; Naruse et al., 2017; Woollacott and Shumway-Cook, 2002). Impulsive aggression is also frequently observed in ADHD (Connor et al., 2010). ADHD is the most common childhood psychiatric disorder worldwide, with approximately 5% of school age children affected by the disorder (Faraone and Larsson, 2018). Due to its complex aetiology and manifestation, there are currently no laboratory-based tests capable of diagnosing ADHD. ADHD often appears comorbid with other psychiatric disorders such as depressive syndromes, substance use disorder (SUD), autism spectrum disorder (ASD) and anxiety disorders which may complicate both diagnosis and treatment (Reimherr et al., 2017; Skoglund et al., 2017; Visser et al., 2016). In addition, several authors describe a substantial overlap of ADHD with developmental coordination disorders (Bax, 1999; Kadesjö and Gillberg, 1998; Rasmussen and Gillberg, 2000). While previously considered a primarily childhood-limited disorder, the prevalence and impact of adult ADHD has become an increasingly active area of research. Longitudinal follow-up studies of ADHD children and population based epidemiological studies have estimated that up to two-thirds of children with ADHD will continue to have impairing ADHD symptoms as adults (Faraone and Larsson, 2018).

Several independent studies have found associations between polymorphisms in the *ADGRL3* gene and an increased risk of developing both ADHD and SUD (Arcos-Burgos et al., 2010; Ribasés et al., 2011; Uhl et al., 2008b; Uhl et al., 2008a). *ADGRL3*, also known as Lathophilin 3 (LPHN3), is expressed at both the pre- and post-synaptic terminals of interneuronal contacts, strongly indicating its role in synapse development and/or function (O'Sullivan et al., 2014). Therefore, alteration in the expression of *ADGRL3* might affect the correct formation and maintenance of neuronal circuits, leading to neurodevelopmental disorders such as ADHD. Some functions of *ADGRL3* at synaptic terminals are mediated by the formation of a trimeric complex with Fibronectin Leucine Rich Transmembrane Protein 3 (FLRT3) and Unc-5 Netrin Receptor C (UNC5). This complex is supportive of both glutamatergic synapse development and transcellular adhesion (Jackson et al., 2015).

Interestingly, despite the absence of known human risk variants in *ADGRL3* coding regions, several of the ADHD-associated single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) and haplotypes that have been reported to confer increased risk of ADHD are located in non-coding evolutionarily conserved regions (ECR) of *ADGRL3*. One of these risk ECR haplotypes (the rs2271338 G>A) was found to reduce luciferase activity by $\approx 40\%$ in B35 neuroblastoma and U87 astrocytoma cell lines as well as leading to decreased thalamic expression of *ADGRL3* in human post-mortem samples from neuropathologically confirmed controls (Martinez et al., 2016). The haplotype leads to the disruption of the binding site of a crucial neurodevelopmental transcription factor. These results suggest that reduced expression of *ADGRL3* might be underpinning the increased risk of ADHD, a mechanism that has been the subject of previous research via downregulation or depletion of *ADGRL3* expression in both animal and cellular models (Lange et al., 2012; Martinez et al., 2016; Orsini et al., 2016; van der Voet et al., 2016; Wallis et al., 2012).

Molecular and anatomical analysis of these animal models provide evidence that is strongly indicative of a disruption in their dopaminergic system. Zebrafish larvae with *adgrl3.1* translation blocked by morpholino (MO) injection were found to have a reduced number of dopamine (DA) neurons in the posterior tuberculum (PT), a region known to be of vital importance to the zebrafish DA system (Lange et al., 2012). However, a similar analysis in lathophilin knockdown flies did not detect a reduced number of dopaminergic neurons. Both a candidate gene and hypothesis-free whole brain RNA-sequencing approach have found disruption of *Dat* gene expression in *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice (Orsini et al., 2016; Wallis et al., 2012). Complementing this evidence, behavioural examinations of genetically modified experimental models of *ADGRL3* have found various aspects of cognitive impairment which may represent ADHD endophenotypes. The disruption or silencing of the *ADGRL3* orthologue expression in mouse, zebrafish and *Drosophila* has consistently been shown to result in increased locomotor activity across species (Lange et al., 2012; Orsini et al., 2016; van der Voet et al., 2016; Wallis et al., 2012) suggesting a highly conserved role of this gene throughout evolution. Up to now, only a recent paper from Orsini and collaborators (Orsini et al., 2016) has reported further behavioural analysis, besides locomotor activity. In this study, *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice displayed increased levels of motivation to complete tasks in exchange for food alongside increased latency to immobility in the forced swim test which may be indicative of reduced behavioural despair or a consequence of the generally high level of activity.

The hyperactivity seen in *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice seems to be a common feature/endophenotype in several rodent models of ADHD such as transgenic knock-out of *Slc6a3* (dopamine transporter) mice and selectively breed spontaneous hypertensive rats (Leo and Gainetdinov,

2013; Sagvolden, 2000). Therefore, *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice also constitute an excellent approach to analyse the cellular roles of ADGRL3 in relation to ADHD.

In our study, we have performed a comprehensive characterization of the behaviour of *Adgrl3* transgenic mice including an analysis of age-matched *Adgrl3*^{+/-} individuals in many cases. Our results have expanded the behavioural defects far beyond the state of the art. Inactivation of ADGRL3 not only triggers the classical hyperactivity of the disorder, it also induces impulsivity, memory deficits and a clear impairment of social behaviours. Moreover, our work is the first in any animal model to perform an analysis of animals showing a moderate loss of ADGRL3 (*Adgrl3*^{+/-} mice). Interestingly, in all tests in which heterozygote animals were included, they did not display any significant alteration. In addition, and with the aim to dissect the molecular mechanisms and identify candidate pathways influencing all these phenotypes downstream of *Adgrl3*, we used deep RNA sequencing of 3 critical ADHD-linked brain regions (prefrontal cortex, hippocampus and striatum). We compare expression levels in 12 *Adgrl3*^{+/+} mice to 12 *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice. Interestingly, our analysis highlights that besides dysregulation in the dopamine pathway, a relatively high number of genes are dysregulated in the prefrontal cortex, while several genes coding for neuro-hormones and peptides involved in the motor and reward systems were differentially expressed in the mouse striatum of *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice.

Methods

Generation of *Adgrl3*-deficient mice

The transgenic mouse line used in this manuscript has already been described in detail in (Wallis et al., 2012). Frozen sperm from *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice (B6;129S4-Lphn3Gt (FHCRC-GT-S17-5H1)Sor) was transferred from Texas A&M Institute for Genomic Medicine (Mutant Mouse Regional Resource Centers) and re-derived by *in vitro* fertilization and implantation in C57BL/6J dams at the Centre for Experimental Molecular Medicine (ZEMM), University of Würzburg. In order to confirm the deletion of ADGRL3, we measured protein levels in the mouse brain by Western Blot. Details of methods used for Western Blot analysis are available in the Supplementary Information.

Animal husbandry

Mice were housed under standard conditions detailed in the Supplementary Information. In order to reduce suffering and stress of the animals, the least stressful behavioural paradigms were performed first. Animals were habituated to the experimenter by daily handling from birth. Behavioural tests were performed to assess anxiety-like behaviour, locomotive activity, recognition, memory/learning and spatial memory in a cohort of adult *Adgrl3*^{+/+} (n=28, 12 males and 16 females), *Adgrl3*^{+/-} (n=20, 10 males and 10 females) and *Adgrl3*^{-/-} (n=19, 11 males and 8 females) mice. In addition, both social interaction (*Adgrl3*^{+/+} n=12, 8 males and 4 females and *Adgrl3*^{-/-} n=12, 9 males and 3 females) and gait movements (*Adgrl3*^{+/+} n=13, 7 Males and 6 Females and *Adgrl3*^{-/-} n=12, 8 males and 4 females) were investigated in a second cohort of mice. Aggression (*Adgrl3*^{+/+} n=10 and *Adgrl3*^{-/-} n=9) and impulsivity (*Adgrl3*^{+/+} n=7 and *Adgrl3*^{-/-} n=9) were also tested in adult male mice.

Animal protocols have been approved by the boards of the University of Würzburg and the Government of Lower Franconia (license 55.2-2531.01-30/14) and performed according to the European Community guidelines for animal care and use.

Behavioural assessment

All behavioural tests were carefully selected to be adequate to analyse the main features described for ADHD (Association, 2013) as well as some relevant comorbid conditions. In order to reduce suffering and stress of the animals, the least stressful behavioural paradigms were performed first. The light-dark box reveals emotional dysregulation (Crawley and Goodwin, 1980; Onaivi and Martin, 1989). The open-field test highlights hyperactivity as well as anxiety-like behaviour (Post et al., 2011; Seibenhener and Wooten, 2015), while the gait analysis allows detection of other locomotor deficits (Hetze et al., 2012). The novel object recognition task and the Barnes Maze provide information regarding learning and memory dysfunction (Leger et al., 2013; Lueptow, 2017; Pitts, 2018). The social interaction and the resident-intruder tests help to give insight into the presence of antisocial and violent behaviour (Koolhaas et al., 2013; Moy et al., 2004). Finally, the continuous performance test permits recognition of impulsivity and alterations in attention in a paradigm that resembles the human test (Caballero-Puntiverio et al., 2019). Additional information regarding behavioural tests can be found in the supplementary information file.

Light-Dark box

The light-dark box (LDB) test was performed to measure anxiety-like behaviour. This test is based on the conflict between the exploration of unknown areas and the avoidance of brightly lit open spaces. The LDB apparatus consisted of an opaque white box (50x50x40 cm) with an

insert separating the light region from a dark region. Two thirds of the box consisted of the light region and the whole box was semi-permeable to infrared light (TSE Systems, Bad Homburg, Germany). The illumination in the dark compartment was between 0 and 5 lx, while illumination in the lit compartment was approximately 100 lx. Each individual mouse was placed in the dark section of the box and behaviour was recorded for 10 min by an infrared-sensitive CCD camera that was positioned above the centre of the box and controlled by VideoMot2 software (TSE Systems). The latency to enter and time spent in the lit compartment were analysed as measures of anxiety-like behaviour; total distance travelled was also evaluated.

Open-Field

The open field (OF) test was used to measure locomotive/hyperactive behaviour as well as anxiety-like behaviour. The OF consisted of an opaque quadratic box (50x50x40 cm) semipermeable to infrared light (TSE Systems) with an illuminated floor (between 50 and 100 lx from the walls to the centre of the box). Mice were individually placed in one corner of the box and their movements automatically recorded during a 30-min period. Recording was performed by an infrared-sensitive CCD camera that was positioned above the centre of the box and controlled by VideoMot2 software (TSE Systems). This software was used to evaluate the distance travelled and the duration of vertical rears as measures of locomotor activity, as well as the time each mouse spent in the central area as a measure of anxiety-like behaviour.

Gait analysis

GaitLab is an automated quantitative gait analysis system for rodents (Chedly et al., 2017), based on the CatWalk Method (Caballero-Garrido et al., 2017). We used a novel automated gait analysis system developed by Viewpoint Behavioural Technology (Lyon, France) to detect gait abnormalities. Over a period of four days, mice were trained to run smoothly across a narrow glass corridor (7x90 cm). After this initial training period, each mouse's gait and ambulatory movements were recorded over four trials using a high-speed camera (150 frames/s). Only trials in which mouse paw positions and moving speed could be accurately detected were used in the final analysis. The vertical distance travelled by a paw was defined as its stride length. Stance time was defined as the period during motion when a paw was in contact with the ground. The period of motion during which a paw is in the air was defined as the swing time. The vertical distance between the left and right forelimb or left and right hind limb was defined as the fore and hind limb gaps. The horizontal distance between fore and hind limb pairs including the body span in between was defined as the fore and hind base of support (BOS). All parameters were analysed using the specialised Gaitlab analysis software (Viewpoint Behavioural Technology).

Novel object recognition task

The novel object recognition (NOR) task was used to measure memory and object discrimination. The task was performed in the OF box, to which the animals had already been habituated; objects were located in the upper left and lower right corner of the arena. During the first trial (T1) two identical aluminium counters were used as objects. The second trial (T2) was performed 24 h later and one of the counters was replaced with a transparent glass bottle and blue lid. The counter which was replaced was alternated to prevent possible effects of side preference. Each object was thoroughly cleaned with 70% ethanol between individual trials to prevent olfactory cues. Behaviour was recorded using an infrared sensitive CCD camera and analysed with VideoMot2 (TSE Systems). The time spent in the immediate area surrounding each object was recorded during T1 and T2. In T2, the preference for the novel

object was defined as the time spent interacting with the novel object minus the time spent interacting with the familiar object. The time spent interacting with the objects in each trial was assessed along with the preference for the novel object in T2 and total distance travelled in each trial.

Barnes maze

The Barnes maze (BM) was performed to assess visuospatial learning and memory. The apparatus consisted of a circular grey platform, 120 cm in diameter with 40 holes located around its circumference each 5 cm in diameter (TSE Systems). One of the holes contained an escape box. Visual cues were located around the platform to allow visuospatial orientation. Each mouse was individually placed in the centre of the maze in a solid grey cylinder to prevent orientation. The cylinder was removed, and behaviour was recorded for a maximum of three minutes or until the mouse found and entered the escape box. Mice were trained to find the hidden box for 4 days in a total of 10 trials (acquisition phase). The position of the escape box was then changed and a subset of the mice (*Adgrl3*^{+/+} n=19 and *Adgrl3*^{-/-} n=13) were tested over 2 days in 6 trials which composed the reverse learning phase. Behaviour was recorded using an infrared sensitive CCD camera and analysed with VideoMot2 (TSE Systems). Automatically measured parameters were latency to escape along with distance travelled. The number of primary errors, defined as the number of times a mouse poked its head into an incorrect hole was manually scored.

Social Interaction

The social interaction (SI) test was used to measure sociability and preference for social novelty. The SI test was performed in the OF box. All mice were behaviourally naïve and were allowed to habituate to the testing chamber for a 10-min period immediately prior to the first trial of SI. In the first 10-min trial (sociability test, T1), mice were given a choice between exploring an unfamiliar mouse that was enclosed in a small wire cage or an identical empty cage. The small cages were located in the upper left and lower right corner. The position of the cage containing the mouse vs. the empty cage was alternated between trials to prevent possible effects of side preference. 24 hours later, in the second 10-min trial (test of preference for social novelty, T2), mice were given a choice between exploring the first, now familiar mouse or a novel, unfamiliar mouse. Both the novel and unfamiliar mouse were enclosed in the same identical wire cages as during the sociability test. Behaviour was recorded using an infrared sensitive CCD camera and analysed with VideoMot2 (TSE Systems). The time spent in the area surrounding either the mouse or empty cage was assessed during T1 and sociability was defined as interaction time with a wild-type mouse over an empty cage. The time spent in the areas surrounding the novel or the familiar mouse was recorded in T2. Preference for social novelty was defined as time spent interacting with the novel mouse over the familiar mouse. Total distance travelled by mice was recorded in both trials.

Resident-Intruder

The resident-intruder test is based on the territorial behaviour that naturally occurs in male mice and thus it can be used to evaluate aggressive behaviour (Koolhaas et al., 2013). Resident mice were single housed for a minimum of three weeks prior to testing to induce strong territorial behaviour. However, isolated animals can still smell, hear and partially see the other mice in the housing room. Novel wild-type intruder mice were grouped-housed and paired with a larger resident in order to reduce aggressive behaviour of the intruder mouse towards the resident. Each resident-intruder encounter lasted ten minutes from the introduction of the intruder mouse. Trials were recorded using a Logitech webcam and

Windows computer system. Attacks were defined as a physical struggle between the resident and intruder, which was initiated by the resident. The presence or absence of an attack, latency to attack and number of attacks were scored manually.

Continuous performance test (CPT)

The continuous performance test was performed using touchscreen operant chambers to measure the impulsivity and general cognitive ability of male *Adgrl3*^{+/+} and *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice. CPT training consisted of a habituation stage, three training stages, and four probe sessions. The habituation stage was composed of two 20-min sessions to allow the animals to habituate to the touchscreen chamber as well as the reward. During the first training stage (Stage 1- Touch Training) mice were trained to touch a white square (3.5x3.5 cm) presented on the touchscreen inside a white frame. If the mouse touched the screen during the limited hold (LH) period (defined as the stimulus duration plus a 0.5-s interval after stimulus removal) the response was recorded as a 'Hit' and the reward was delivered. If the mouse failed to touch the response area within the LH period, then a 'Miss' was recorded. During the second stage (Stage 2 – S+) the white square was changed to a target stimulus (S+): a black and white image of horizontal stripes (3.5 x 3.5 cm). In the final training stage (Stage 3 – two-stimulus discrimination) during 50% of the trials, a new non-target stimulus (a black and white image of a 'snowflake', S-) was presented in the response area. If the mouse touched the screen during the LH period of the S+ stimulus, a hit was recorded and the reward delivered. If the mouse did not touch the screen during the LH period of S- stimulus a Correct rejection was recorded, if the mouse did touch the screen a False Alarm was recorded. Following stage 3, the four probe trials were conducted. During these trials the following parameters were adjusted in order to increase the difficulty of the task: Probe 1 – stimulus duration, Probe 2 – stimulus contrast, Probe 3 – Inter-trial interval and Probe 4 – S+ vs S- probability.

The following events were defined and counted during the Stage 3 and probe trials: Hits (correct responses to S+), Misses (failures to respond to S+), Correct rejections (successfully withholding responses to S-) and False Alarms (incorrect responses to S-). The following parameters were then calculated for Stage 3 and the probe trials: Hit rate (HR = Hits/(Hits+Misses)), False alarm rate (FAR = False alarms/(False alarms + Correct rejection)), sensitivity d' (the ability to discriminate between S+ and S-; $d' = z(\text{HR}) - z(\text{FAR})$), and response bias c (the tendency to favour one way of responding to stimuli over another; $c = 0.5[z(\text{HR}) + z(\text{FAR})]$). Detailed descriptions of the test procedures and parameters measured are available in Supplemental Information.

Dissection of ADHD-Relevant brain regions and RNA-sequencing

12 *Adgrl3*^{+/+} and 12 *Adgrl3*^{-/-} adult mice that were behaviourally naïve (age between postnatal day (P) 65 and P76; mean=P67.15, SD=3.46) were anesthetized with a lethal dose of isoflurane and sacrificed by cervical dislocation. Brains were dissected, frozen immediately in dry ice-cold isopentane and stored at -80°C until dissection of the relevant brain areas. The prefrontal cortex, hippocampus and striatum were separated on a pre-cooled plate and RNA was isolated with the AllPrep DNA/RNA/miRNA Universal Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany). The cDNA libraries for each brain region were prepared using the standard Illumina protocol (Illumina, GmbH, Munich, Germany). Following this preparation, all libraries were sequenced with High Output 2 × 75 cycles kit using the Nextseq sequencing platform that generated 75 bp long single end reads. After the removal of original cDNA templates, a total of ~400 million raw reads were produced that were later processed and analysed.

Behavioural Data Analysis

For the majority of behavioural test paradigms, genotype effects on behavioural data were analysed by two-sided univariate analysis of variance (ANOVA). In addition, the genotype difference for baseline increased reward retrieval latency was examined using a t-test and the genotype difference in presence/absence of attack during the resident-intruder trial was tested using Fisher's exact test. In cases of significance (defined as $p < 0.05$), appropriate *post hoc* comparisons were performed using correction for multiple testing; the specific *post hoc* test used is noted in each case. For behavioural tests with repeated measures, a repeated measures mixed analysis of variance was used, with genotype as between-subject factor and time or testing phase as the repeated measure. Behavioural data fit parametric assumptions and analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism 7 (GraphPad Software, La Jolla, CA, USA).

Sequencing Data Analysis

The raw reads were processed using FastQC 0.11.4 for assessing read quality, number of duplicates and presence of adapter sequences. After this, the Illumina TruSeq adaptors were cleaved using cutadapt version 1.16 and resulting reads were further trimmed keeping a quality drop value below a mean of Q20 (Martin, 2011). Further, the processed sequences were mapped to the murine genome (mm16, GRCm38) using the short-read aligner STAR-2.5.2b with genome and annotation files retrieved from GENCODE (Dobin et al., 2013). For all the studied samples, the proportion of reads mapped to the mouse reference genome ranged between 89% and 91% in total. The sequences aligning to specific genes were quantified using BEDtools subcommand intersect (version 2.25.0) (Quinlan and Hall, 2010). Global normalization of read counts was performed followed by independent analysis of each brain region to identify differentially expressed genes using DESeq2 version 1.16.1 (Love et al., 2014). For the combined brain region analysis, read counts were summed across the three brain regions prior to the analysis with DESeq2. Only the genes having a Benjamini-Hochberg corrected p-value below 0.05 were classified as significantly differentially expressed genes (DEGs). The data were represented as MA plot using the DESeq2 function plotMA. All RNA-Seq data presented in this work have been deposited at the NCBI Gene Expression Omnibus and can be accessed through GEO series accession number GSE117357 (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSE117357>) (Edgar et al., 2002).

Gene Set Enrichment Analysis and Pathway Analysis

In order to better interpret the biological relevance of DEGs, KEGG based gene-set enrichment analysis (GSEA) was performed using Enricher (Chen et al., 2013; Kuleshov et al., 2016). Only genes with at least a 50 % increase or decrease in gene expression were included for GSEA. Each brain region's DEGs were separated based on the direction of expression change. The minimum required number of genes for GSEA was set at 10 genes. Only the set of PFC downregulated genes was sufficiently large. Over-representation of genes in a particular KEGG pathway was determined using the Fisher's exact test followed by appropriate imputation-based correction for multiple testing.

The over-representation of DEGs from a specific brain region on annotated terms reflecting biological functions and pathways was also assessed using the Ingenuity Pathway Analysis software (IPA) (Ingenuity Systems, Redwood City, CA, USA; www.ingenuity.com). IPA software takes account of the size and direction of logFC allowing for the inclusion of all DEGs in a brain region in a single analysis. IPA was used to test for an over-representation of DEGs in annotated terms representing various biological and disease pathways. The Fisher's exact test followed by Benjamini-Hochberg correction to a threshold of 0.05 was used to

determine statistically significant pathway enrichment. The top 25 gene networks were also constructed by IPA taking into account the direction and magnitude of genes' log fold changes. Gene networks with a network score ($-\log_{10}(\text{p-value})$) over 8 were considered relevant. IPA was also used to test for an over-representation of differentially expressed genes which were previously implicated in ADHD. The 436 genes included in the list of ADHD-associated genes were compiled from the combination of the ADHD gene database (<http://adhd.psych.ac.cn/index.do>) and a comprehensive search for published reviews of ADHD genetic and pharmacogenetic studies. The full list of genes is available in (Pagerols et al., 2018) supplemental information 1. To obtain meaningful biological and statistical results, analysis was restricted to pathways which included ≥ 2 DEG.

Results

ADGRL3 protein is absent in *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice and partially reduced in *Adgrl3*^{+/-} mice

A large band corresponding to the p120 subunit of ADGRL3 was clearly visible in the *Adgrl3*^{+/+} mice prefrontal cortex lysates and was completely absent from *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice samples while an intermediate density band was visible for *Adgrl3*^{+/-} mice (Fig. 1). These results show there is a clear *Adgrl3* gene dosage effect controlling ADGRL3 protein levels.

Adgrl3 depletion does not alter anxiety-like behaviour in the Light-Dark Box

No significant genotype differences were found in the latency to enter the light region (Fig. 2a) or the amount of time spent in the light region (Figure 2b), two common measures of anxiety-like behaviour (Latency $F(2,65)=1.958$; $p=0.1493$, Time $F(2,65)=0.1617$; $p=0.8510$). A significant genotype effect was observed on the global distance travelled (Figure 2c) in the LDB ($F(2,65)=9.033$; $p=0.0003$). *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice were found to display increased locomotor activity (*Adgrl3*^{-/-} vs *Adgrl3*^{+/+} ($p=0.0004$) and *Adgrl3*^{-/-} vs *Adgrl3*^{+/-} ($p=0.0043$), Tukey's multiple comparison test).

Hyperactivity of *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice in the Open Field

A significant genotype effect was observed on the time spent rearing (Figure 3a, $F(2,64)=31.16$; $p<0.0001$). The average time spent rearing of *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice was over two fold less than the rearing time of either *Adgrl3*^{+/-} or *Adgrl3*^{+/+} mice (*Adgrl3*^{-/-} vs *Adgrl3*^{+/-} ($p<0.0001$), *Adgrl3*^{-/-} vs *Adgrl3*^{+/+} ($p<0.0001$), Tukey's multiple comparison test). The amount of time mice spent in the centre of the OF (Figure 3b), another common measure of anxiety, was unaffected by genotype ($F(2,64)=2.746$; $p=0.0717$). The distance travelled (Figure 3c) by mice was found to have a very large genotype effect ($F(2,64)=28.06$; $p<0.0001$). *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice showed an over two-fold average increase in global distance when compared to *Adgrl3*^{+/-} or *Adgrl3*^{+/+} mice (*Adgrl3*^{-/-} vs *Adgrl3*^{+/-} ($p<0.0001$), *Adgrl3*^{-/-} vs *Adgrl3*^{+/+} ($p<0.0001$), Tukey's multiple comparison test). The reduced rearing time of *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice is likely the result of their hyperactivity. Supplementary videos 1, 2 and 3 show a representative video of the performance in the OF test of *Adgrl3*^{+/+}, *Adgrl3*^{+/-} and *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice, respectively. A deeper analysis of the distance travelled in intervals of 5 minutes (Supplementary figure 1) showed that *Adgrl3*^{+/+} and *Adgrl3*^{+/-} mice habituate to the OF (shown as a reduction in the distance travelled over the 30-min period), while, as expected, *Adgrl3*^{-/-} animals failed to habituate and maintain a similar distance travelled over time.

Adgrl3^{-/-} mice have altered gait with reduced stance time and a wider base of support

Qualitative observation of the locomotion and performance of *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice in the OF test (see Supplementary Video 3) suggested the presence of gait disturbances in knockout animals. This observation led us to perform a more thorough gait analysis of *Adgrl3*^{+/+} and *Adgrl3*^{-/-} animals by using the Gaitlab system. Particularly, the stride frequency (Figure 4a) was not significantly different between genotypes ($F(1,96)=2.882$; Genotype: $p=0.0928$). The stride length (Figure 4b) was also not found to be significantly different between genotypes ($F(1,96)=0.0268$; $p=0.8704$). By contrast, *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice showed a significant reduction in overall stance time (Figure 4c) in comparison to controls ($F(1,96)=9.949$; $p=0.0021$). Analysis of individual paws also found a significant difference between genotypes for the stance time of the left hind paw (*Adgrl3*^{+/+} vs *Adgrl3*^{-/-} LF $p=0.4549$, RF $p=0.2349$, LH $p=0.0421$, RH $p=0.9944$, Sidak's multiple comparisons test). No significant difference in swing time (Figure 4d) between genotypes was observed ($F(1,96)=2.857$; $p=0.0942$). The fore and hind limb gaps (Figure 4e) were not significantly different between genotypes

($F(1,45)=0.2331$; Genotype $p=0.6316$). *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice had a significantly wider BOS than controls (Figure 4f, $F(1,45)=19.89$; Genotype $p<0.0001$). Independent fore and hind BOS analysis with appropriate multiple correction revealed this genotype difference was significant for both fore and hind limbs (*Adgrl3*^{+/+} vs *Adgrl3*^{-/-} Fore Limb $p=0.0048$, Hind Limb $p=0.0069$, Sidak's multiple comparison test). The presence of reduced stance time in *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice may be a result of the hyperactivity observed across tests while the altered BOS may contribute to the drastically reduced rearing activity seen in these mice. Supplementary videos 4-6 show a representative performance of each genotype.

***Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice show reduced ability to distinguish between novel and familiar objects in the novel object recognition task**

The total amount of time mice spent interacting with objects (Figure 5a) was not significantly different between object exploration (Trial 1) and object recognition (Trial 2) (Trial $F(1,65)=0.0175$; $p=0.8952$). No significant overall genotype effect was found in the percentage of time mice spent exploring objects across both trials (Genotype $F(1,65)=0.0253$; $p=0.7775$). A significant trial by genotype interaction effect was detected, with *Adgrl3*^{+/+} mice showing a significant increase in time spent interacting with the objects during the second trial, while *Adgrl3*^{+/-} and *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice showed no significant difference in interaction time across trials (Trial by Genotype Interaction $F(2,65)=5.054$; $p=0.0091$, Exploration vs Recognition *Adgrl3*^{+/+} $p=0.0162$, *Adgrl3*^{+/-} $p=0.7751$, *Adgrl3*^{-/-} $p=0.5005$, Sidak's multiple comparisons test). During the object recognition trial (Figure 5b), mice showed a significant overall preference for interaction with the novel object ($F(1,130)=15.70$; Object $p=0.0001$). This preference for the novel object was particular to *Adgrl3*^{+/+} and *Adgrl3*^{+/-} mice while no increase in time spent interacting with the novel object in comparison to the familiar object was observed in *Adgrl3*^{-/-} animals (Novel vs Familiar Object: *Adgrl3*^{+/+} $p=0.0008$, *Adgrl3*^{+/-} $p=0.0269$, *Adgrl3*^{-/-} $p=0.8175$, Sidak's multiple comparisons test). *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice therefore spent the same amount of time exploring the objects generally but did not show any preference for the novel object. The absence of a difference in exploration indicates the reduction in preference for novel objects is the result of memory impairment in *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice rather than a reduction in motivation. The total distance travelled during the object recognition trial (Trial 2) (Figure 5c) was significantly less than the total distance travelled during the object exploration trial (Trial 1) (Trial $F(1,65)=6.678$; $p=0.0120$). Multiple comparison analysis revealed a significant reduction in the distance travelled by *Adgrl3*^{+/-} mice in the object recognition trial in comparison to the object exploration trial (Trial *Adgrl3*^{+/+} $p=0.9859$, *Adgrl3*^{+/-} $p=0.0484$, *Adgrl3*^{-/-} $p=0.3490$, Sidak's multiple comparisons test). A significant genotype effect on the total distance travelled in each trial was detected, with *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice showing two fold increased locomotive activity over *Adgrl3*^{+/+} and *Adgrl3*^{+/-} mice (Genotype $F(2,65)=35.89$; $p<0.0001$, *Adgrl3*^{+/+} vs. *Adgrl3*^{+/-} $p=0.6653$, *Adgrl3*^{+/+} vs. *Adgrl3*^{-/-} $p<0.0001$, *Adgrl3*^{+/-} vs. *Adgrl3*^{-/-} $p<0.0001$, Sidak's multiple comparisons test).

***Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice show impaired visuospatial memory in the Barnes Maze**

The decreasing escape latencies, primary errors and global distance travelled across trials shows that all mice were capable of learning the location of the escape box during both the initial acquisition phase (Figure 6a-c) and during the reverse phase (Figure 6d-f) (all three measurements: two-way repeated measures ANOVA: Session in Acquisition Phase $p<0.0001$ and Session in Reversal Phase $p<0.0001$). There were no significant trial by genotype interactions for either escape latencies or primary errors in either learning phase. A significant trial by genotype interaction was found for global distance travelled during the acquisition phase with the increased distance travelled by *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice most prominent

during the early trials (T1-T4) (Session by Genotype Interaction $F(18,585)=2.721$; $p=0.0002$). During the acquisition phase, escape latency (Figure 6a) was found to be significantly different between genotypes with Tukey's multiple comparisons test showing *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice have a significantly increased latency compared to heterozygous or wild-type mice ($F(2,65)=5.769$; Genotype $p=0.0049$, *Adgrl3*^{+/+} vs. *Adgrl3*^{-/-} $p=0.0054$, *Adgrl3*^{+/-} vs. *Adgrl3*^{+/+} $p=0.0260$, Tukey's multiple comparisons test). *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice also showed a significantly increased number of primary errors (Figure 6b) over wild-type but not heterozygous mice, while heterozygous mice made more errors than wild-type mice ($F(2,65)=5.501$; Genotype $p<0.0001$, *Adgrl3*^{+/+} vs. *Adgrl3*^{-/-} $p=0.0092$, *Adgrl3*^{+/-} vs. *Adgrl3*^{+/+} $p=0.0469$, Tukey's multiple comparisons test). *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice travelled a greater distance (Figure 6c) during the acquisition phase than *Adgrl3*^{+/-} or *Adgrl3*^{+/+} mice (Genotype $F(2,65)=16.46$; $p<0.0001$, *Adgrl3*^{+/+} vs. *Adgrl3*^{-/-} $p=0.0017$, *Adgrl3*^{+/-} vs. *Adgrl3*^{-/-} $p<0.0001$, Tukey's multiple comparisons test). Multiple comparisons analyses also revealed a significant reduction in the global distance travelled of *Adgrl3*^{+/-} mice in comparison to wild-types (*Adgrl3*^{+/+} vs. *Adgrl3*^{+/-} $p=0.0028$, Tukey's multiple comparisons test). During the reversal phase, *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice again displayed a significant increase in escape latency and global distance travelled (Figure 6d and 6f) but no significant increase in the number of primary errors (Figure 6e) (Escape Latency: $F(1,30)=4.347$; $p=0.0457$, Primary Errors $F(1,30)=0.8047$; $p=0.3768$ and Distance Travelled $F(1,30)=5.59$; $p=0.0247$). The reduced ability of *Adgrl3*^{-/-} animals to learn and consolidate visuospatial memory may be indicative of hippocampus-based memory deficiency.

***Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice show increased sociability but impairment in social memory in the Social Interaction Test**

Mice showed increased total interaction time (Figure 7a) with the novel and familiar mice in the social novelty trial compared to the total interaction time in the sociability trial (Trial $F(1,22)=26.03$; $p<0.0001$, *Adgrl3*^{+/+} $p=0.0003$, *Adgrl3*^{-/-} $p=0.0275$, Sidak's multiple comparisons test). When comparing total interaction time between the sociability and social novelty trials, no significant overall genotype differences were detected (Genotype $F(1,22)=0.0870$; $p=0.7709$). In the sociability trial (Figure 7b), mice showed an overall significant preference for sociability, defined as an increased interaction time with the cage containing a wild-type mouse over an empty cage (Cage $F(1,44)=4.366$; $p=0.0425$). This increased sociability was clearly evident in *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice, which were found to spend less time interacting with the empty cage and more time with the mouse cage, while *Adgrl3*^{+/+} mice showed no significant difference in cage preference (Genotype by Cage Interaction ($F(1,44)=6.972$; $p=0.0114$, *Adgrl3*^{+/+} $p=0.9092$, *Adgrl3*^{-/-} $p=0.0034$, Sidak's multiple comparisons test). During the social novelty trial (Figure 7c), mice showed a significant overall preference for social novelty, defined as an increased time spent interacting with the novel mouse cage over the familiar mouse cage (Cage $F(1,44)=4.869$; $p=0.0326$). This increase in social novelty was confined to *Adgrl3*^{+/+} mice; no such preference for social novelty was detected in *Adgrl3*^{-/-} (*Adgrl3*^{+/+} $p=0.0278$, *Adgrl3*^{-/-} $p=0.8213$, Sidak's multiple comparisons test). Similarly to the results observed by Kogan and collaborators (Kogan et al., 2000), the presence of increased sociability in *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice coupled with reduced preference for social novelty is strongly indicative of impairment in social memory consolidation. The total distance travelled by mice during the social novelty trial (Figure 7d) was significantly less than the total distance during the sociability trial (Trial $F(1,22)=8.489$; $p=0.0080$). *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice showed a significant reduction in distance travelled while control mice showed no significant difference (*Adgrl3*^{+/+} $p=0.3424$, *Adgrl3*^{-/-} $p=0.0224$, Sidak's multiple comparisons test).

Inactivation of *Adgrl3* results in an absence of aggression in the Resident-Intruder Paradigm

Comparison of the presence/absence of attacks by *Adgrl3*^{+/+} and *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice (Figure 8) during the trial revealed significant genotype difference (Fisher's Exact Test $p=0.0007$). It was planned to record residents' number of attacks and latency to attack but these measurements were not possible due to the complete absence of any attacks by *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice. In contrast to the lack of aggression of *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice, 8 out of 10 of the *Adgrl3*^{+/+} resident mice attacked the intruder mouse. The depletion of *Adgrl3* therefore results in a dramatic decrease in the aggression of these mice.

Adgrl3^{-/-} mice show increased impulsivity and reduced motivation for food in the Continuous performance test (CPT)

There were no genotype differences in the number of sessions to reach the criterion in any of the training stages (Figure 9a), therefore we did not detect gross cognitive differences between *Adgrl3*^{+/+} and *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice. During Stage 3 training, HR and sensitivity (d') increased (Session: $F(6,84)=11.92$; $p<0.0001$; $F(6,84)=27.50$; $p<0.0001$, respectively), FAR decreased (main effect of session: $F(6,84)=9.94$; $p<0.0001$), while response bias (c) remained unchanged across sessions (Figure 9b). Although HR, sensitivity and response bias were similar across training sessions in *Adgrl3*^{+/+} and *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice, FAR was consistently higher in the *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice compared to *Adgrl3*^{+/+} mice (Genotype: $F(1,84)=5.92$; $p=0.0289$). Two last sessions of the CPT training were averaged to yield the measures of baseline responding. There were no genotype differences in either HR, FAR, d' or c at baseline performance. Additionally, both correct and incorrect response latencies were similar in *Adgrl3*^{+/+} and *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice. Interestingly, compared to *Adgrl3*^{+/+} mice, higher reward retrieval latency was observed in *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice ($t(14)=2.947$; $p=0.0106$), which might indicate reduced food motivation in these animals. Moreover, the number of screen touches during the ITI (Figure 9c) were significantly higher in the *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice (381.7 ± 38.6) compared to *Adgrl3*^{+/+} mice (187 ± 36.0) ($t(16)=3.451$; $p=0.0033$), a finding which suggests higher impulsivity in *Adgrl3*^{-/-} animals.

After animals had acquired the CPT, we studied the effects of modifications to baseline parameters on the performance in *Adgrl3*^{+/+} and *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice. In Probe 1 (variable stimulus duration), both S+ and S- stimulus duration was shortened (Figure 10). Predictably, HR and d' decreased with reducing stimulus durations (Stimulus Duration: $F(5,84)=6.28$; $p<0.0001$ and $F(5,84)=16.88$; $p<0.0001$, respectively). FAR increased at shorter stimulus durations (Stimulus Duration: $F(5,84)=4.27$; $p=0.0017$) in both genotypes, but to a higher extent in the *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice (main effect of genotype: $F(1,84)=5.42$; $p=0.0223$). In Probe 2 (variable stimulus contrast), the contrast of the S+ and S- images was modified without altering the overall luminance of the images. HR remained stable, while FAR increased (Stimulus Contrast: $F(3,56)=24.62$; $p<0.0001$) and d' and c decreased ($F(3,56)=27.89$; $p<0.0001$ and $F(3,56)=5.79$; $p=0.0016$, respectively) with reducing stimulus contrast. Across all stimulus contrasts, *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice appeared to have a higher HR (Genotype: $F(1,56)=9.35$; $p=0.0034$), higher FAR (Genotype: $F(1,56)=10.81$; $p=0.0017$), and a more liberal response bias (lower c , Genotype: $F(1,56)=13.26$; $p<0.001$). In Probe 3 (long ITI), no genotype- or parameter-dependent effects on task performance were found (Figure 11). Finally, in Probe 4 (S+ probability), only FAR was affected by reduced (30% of trials) proportion of S+ presentation (S+ probability: $F(1,30)=4.40$; $p=0.044$). Again, *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice had overall higher FAR (main effect of genotype: $F(1,30)=4.71$; $p=0.0380$) compared to *Adgrl3*^{+/+} animals. The higher FAR of *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice may be also indicative of an increase in impulsivity.

Transcriptomic analysis of brain regions reveals differential gene expression

Principal component analysis of all sequenced samples grouped into three distinct clusters corresponding to the brain regions sequenced (Supplementary Figures 2-3). The PFC contained the largest number (180) of genes with statistically significant differential expression following multiple-correction. Of these 180 genes, 115 (63.9%) were upregulated in the *Adgrl3*^{-/-} PFC. Only 24 of these statistically significant differentially expressed genes (DEG) display a two-fold difference in gene expression levels (Table 1). Two of the 115 PFC upregulated genes (interleukin 31 (Il31) and starch binding domain 1 (*Stbd1*)) displayed an average log₂ Fold Change (logFC) greater than 1 (logFC Il31= 1.86, logFC *Stbd1*=1.97), signifying an over two-fold increase in expression. In contrast, 22 of the 65 downregulated genes showed an at least 50% drop in expression levels as indicated by a logFC of less than -1. Interestingly, the most downregulated (logFC=-3.03) gene in the PFC was solute carrier family 6, member 3 (*Slc6a3*), a gene which codes for the dopamine transporter (DAT). The hippocampus had 36 genes with statistically significant differential expression across mouse genotypes. As seen in the PFC, a majority of DEG were upregulated (23 genes, 63.9%) in the *Adgrl3*^{-/-} hippocampus compared to wild-type mice. Only two genes showed an absolute logFC greater than 1. As was the case in the PFC, *Stbd1* was over two-fold upregulated (logFC=1.82) in the *Adgrl3*^{-/-} hippocampus. Perilipin 4 (*Plin4*) showed a greater than 50% reduction in expression levels (logFC=-1.11) in the *Adgrl3*^{-/-} hippocampus (Table 1). From the three brain regions, the striatum showed the smallest number (22) of statistically significant differential regulated genes across mouse genotypes. The direction of expression change was evenly split between up and downregulated genes (11 each). 6 of these genes had an absolute logFC greater than 1 (Table 1). One of these genes, shroom family member 3 (*Shroom3*), had a reduction in gene expression in the *Adgrl3*^{-/-} striatum, while the five remaining genes had an increase in expression levels in *Adgrl3*^{-/-} striatum. The most upregulated gene was pro-melanin-concentrating hormone (*Pmch*), which was also the most DEG in any brain region (logFC=5.370832). The *Pmch* gene product is proteolytically modified to produce at least three different protein products: Melanin-Concentrating Hormone (MCH), Neuropeptide-Glutamic Acid-Isoleucine (NEI), and Neuropeptide-Glycine-Glutamic acid (NGE). A subsample of *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice (n=3) displayed markedly increased levels of expression of the five upregulated genes. Principal component analysis showed the overall striatum gene expression profiles of these mice were similar to the other the *Adgrl3*^{+/+} and *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice (Supplementary Figures 2-3). In total, 208 genes were found to be differentially regulated across mouse genotypes, with 134 (64.4%) of these upregulated. 188 of these genes were found to be differentially expressed in only one brain region, the majority of these genes were upregulated (66.0%). 10 genes were differentially expressed in two brain regions while 10 other genes were found to be differentially expressed in all three brain regions. Genes which were differentially expressed in multiple brain regions always had a logFC in the same direction across regions. Of the 10 genes dysregulated in two brain regions, 5 (50%) were upregulated. The same ratio of up/down regulated genes was observed in the genes found to be differentially regulated in all brain regions.

Biologically relevant terms in gene set enrichment and pathway analysis

The PFC downregulated gene set was the only group of genes large enough to meet to conditions to perform GSEA using Enricher (Chen et al. 2013, Kuleshov et al. 2016). A number of KEGG pathways were significantly enriched following correction for multiple testing. The five significantly enriched KEGG Pathways were; cocaine addiction, amphetamine addiction, neuroactive ligand receptor interaction, dopaminergic synapse and Parkinson's disease (Table 2). IPA analysis using all the DEGs in a specific brain region

detected a number of significantly enriched biological and disease associated annotated terms. The most enriched terms for PFC DEGs were Behaviour (Figure 12) and Neurological Diseases (Benjamini-Hochberg testing correction: Behaviour $p=0.000135$, Neurological Diseases $p=0.000305$).

Discussion

Little is known regarding the molecular and cellular functions of ADGRL3. The protein is localised at the synapses of neuronal cells potentially forming a trimeric complex with FLRT3 and UNC5 (Jackson et al., 2015; Ranaivoson et al., 2015). The gene is known to play an important role in neuronal migration and synapse development (Jackson et al., 2016; O'Sullivan et al., 2014). Likely because of such synaptic roles, several studies have found associations of genetic variations in *ADGRL3* with an increased risk of developing ADHD (Arcos-Burgos et al., 2010; Ribasés et al., 2011). Cross-species transgenic *ADGRL3* models have also shown anatomical, molecular and behavioural links to ADHD (Lange et al., 2012; van der Voet et al., 2016; Wallis et al., 2012). The combination of evidence from genetic association studies and experimental models highlights *ADGRL3* as one of the most consistently implicated ADHD-risk genes.

Our results show that the *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice are extremely hyperactive, hypoaggressive and show learning and memory deficits. Our RNA-sequencing analysis has been able to unveil new pathways acting downstream of ADGRL3 deficiency that might underpin the different pathological phenotypes observed in the knockout mice. Remarkably, this is the first work that includes a more exhaustive description of the behaviour of the heterozygous *Adgrl3* mice. Those mice behaved, in contrast to *Adgrl3*^{-/-} littermates, largely similar to *Adgrl3*^{+/+} mice. Such a lack of phenotypes contrasts with the finding that *ADGRL3* risk alleles drive a decrease in expression rather than a complete absence of *ADGRL3* expression (Martinez et al., 2016). However, this is not completely surprising given the various forms of robust genetic and neurobiological redundancy often seen in genetically modified mice (Barbaric et al., 2007). Furthermore, and in agreement with our results, subjects that harbour a specific change leading to a clear reduction of latrophilin expression were considered healthy (Martinez et al., 2016). We can speculate that some reduction of the gene expression increases susceptibility, but it is not sufficient to induce any neuropsychological dysfunction. It is likely that other genomic modifications or environmental (i.e. pre- or postnatal) factors are required to pull the disease trigger.

Our study reproduces the locomotor hyperactivity of *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice previously reported (Wallis et al., 2012). The considerable increased locomotor performance is observed in numerous behavioural paradigms such as the OF, LDB, BM, OR and SI. In addition, we considered gait analysis to be of special interest, since gait dysfunction maybe also present in ADHD patients (Naruse et al., 2017) and can be improved by the current treatments with methylphenidate (Auriel et al., 2006; Möhring et al., 2018). In this regard, the reduced stance time of *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice in the gait analysis can also be considered a sign of hyperactivity. The differential gait movements in *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice including altered fore and hind limb BOS may recapitulate some of the gait abnormalities seen in ADHD patients (Naruse et al., 2017). The second phenotype observed in the *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice is a clear impairment in different forms of memory, a defect that has been frequently associated with ADHD. Orsini and collaborators (Orsini et al., 2016) already performed a working memory test (a lever-based paradigm) but they failed to find a significant difference. This memory paradigm used food as motivation for mice to complete the task. Interestingly, as detected in our CPT analysis, *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice display reduced food motivation and hyperactivity which might explain the observations described by Orsini and collaborators. A second critical difference is that in our study, we use

a larger sample size and more classical and diverse behavioural paradigms to investigate various memory domains of *Adgrl3* transgenic mice. *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice show reduced recall ability for both objects and other mice in the OR and SI paradigms. These results strongly suggest a significant deficit across different memory domains. The decrease in social memory is in contrast to the increased sociability seen in these mice. Data from the Barnes Maze, which is designed to detect differences in spatial memory, also shows that *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice have a deficit in this memory domain. All mice were capable of learning where the escape hole was during the acquisition and reversal phase, which once again suggests an absence of motivational deficit in *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice. The increased number of primary errors and time taken by *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice to escape the maze was therefore likely the result of a spatial memory deficit, although the hyperactivity of *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice as seen in all tasks including the Barnes Maze may also increase escape time independently of any memory deficit. Taken in combination, these memory-based behavioural paradigms indicate that *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice have a general impairment in memory formation and retrieval which may recapitulate the learning and memory endophenotypes seen in some ADHD patients.

The reduced aggression of *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice may also be indicative of an increase in sociability. In agreement with the deficits in memory observed in the Novel Object Recognition task, the reduction in interaction with the novel mouse is therefore likely the result of a memory deficit rather than a reduction in motivation. By contrast, the results of the CPT do not suggest a general cognitive impairment of *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice but an increase in impulsivity due to the higher FAR of these mice compared to wildtype controls. *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice may therefore reiterate the increased impulsivity commonly seen in ADHD patients (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). CPT was chosen because it is a powerful method which provides better comparison to human studies in which CPT is commonly used. In this regard, a study by Fallgatter and colleagues using the CPT in combination with an ongoing EEG in a sample of ADHD patients showed that a risk allele of *ADGRL3* gene affects the number of omission errors during the CPT as well as several measures involved in cognitive response control (Fallgatter et al., 2013).

In addition, our RNA-sequencing approach has provided a robust hypothesis-free transcriptomic analysis of differential gene expression in three ADHD-linked brain regions such as PFC, hippocampus and striatum and has unveiled novel pathways that might play important roles in the function of *ADGRL3* and, in turn, in the etiopathology of ADHD. Such an approach may provide mechanistic insight into how depletion of *Adgrl3* may impact neuronal processes and bring about the strong behavioural phenotypes observed in this mouse model such as hyperactivity, increased impulsivity and memory deficits. Previous transcriptomic analysis of *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mouse by (Orsini et al., 2016) found that cell adhesion molecules, calcium signaling proteins and genes with roles in synaptic neurotransmission were differentially expressed. The design of our study ensured a much higher statistical power, a much deeper analysis and a description of region-specific changes. Importantly, the total numbers of genes found to exhibit differential expression was relatively small, indicating a specific pathway of action, rather than a broad perturbation of neurobiology in *ADGRL3*-deficient animals. The limited number of differentially expressed genes is not surprising considering the complex genetic aetiology of ADHD. Disruption of an individual gene is generally expected to have a subtle impact but may act in connection with other genetic variants and environmental factors to increase the risk of developing ADHD. In *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice the majority of differential expression occurred in the PFC. This brain region is essential for a number of cognitive functions highly relevant to ADHD, in particular self-

regulatory processes such as attention, cognitive flexibility, and impulse control (Kim et al., 2011; Rossi et al., 2009).

The anti-ADHD compound MPH has been shown to preferentially activate dopaminergic transmission within the PFC by targeting DAT and therefore, downregulation of *Slc6a3* expression in the *Adgrl3*^{-/-} PFC is of particular interest. Previous works also found *Slc6a3* to be differentially regulated at level of the whole brain in *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice (Orsini et al., 2016; Wallis et al., 2012), but this is the first region specific finding and provides a valuable target for future study. As outlined previously, the DA system plays a fundamental role in ADHD neuropathology and other *ADGRL3* transgenic models have shown links to this transmitter system (Engert and Pruessner, 2008; Lange et al., 2018). Interestingly, *adgrl3.1*-deficient zebrafish displayed histologic abnormalities in the DA system (Lange et al., 2012) and disruption of *Adgrl* and *Dat* in *Drosophila* results in a highly similar light-sensitive hyperactive phenotype (van der Voet et al., 2016). In addition, as *Slc6a3* mRNA found in the PFC is transported by axons from nuclei in the substantia nigra (SN) and ventral tegmental (VTA), the reduction of *Slc6a3* may also indicate an impairment in the SN and VTA or projections from these regions (D'Ardenne et al., 2012). Notably, the behavioural phenotypes observed in dopamine transporter (DAT) knockout mice, such as spontaneous hyperactivity, impaired learning and memory (Gainetdinov and Caron, 2001, 2000; Trinh et al., 2003; Wong et al., 2012) as well as increased impulsivity (Yamashita et al., 2013), resemble those we observed in *Adgrl3*^{-/-} animals. In addition, mice which have their dopamine transporter levels knocked down to ~ 10% normal expression levels also display a hyperactive phenotype similar to *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice (Kwiatkowski et al., 2017). The finding of behavioural similarities between *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice and DAT knockout/knockdown mice provides further evidence that genetic polymorphisms in *ADGRL3* may confer an increased risk for ADHD through disruption of the DA pathway. In contrast to our results with heterozygous *Adgrl3*^{+/-} mice, animals with intermediate DAT levels display some deficits, although milder than the DAT knockout mice. In this regard, some of the impairments are only observed during adolescence but not in adult DAT heterozygote male animals (Ciampoli et al., 2017; França et al., 2016; Mereu et al., 2017). Moreover, it is possible that 50% downregulation of DAT establishes a pathological threshold, since local knockdown of *Dat* gene leading to 40% reduction in the striatum does not produce any effect on novelty-induced locomotion (Salahpour et al., 2007). We can speculate that such a threshold does not exist for *ADGRL3* or that a higher downregulation or additional triggering factors of genetic or environmental nature are needed to reveal any behavioural phenotype in *Adgrl3*^{+/-} mice. This would also explain that the *Adgrl3*^{+/-} mice analysed in our study do not display any visible phenotype. Although the mechanism underlying the relation between Dopamine and *ADGRL3* is still unknown, we can hypothesise that *ADGRL3* may play a role in the modulation of dopaminergic synapses in a similar way to what is observed in glutamatergic synapses in the mouse cortex and hippocampus, where *ADGRL3* and its interacting partner *FLRT3* are able to regulate glutamatergic synapse number as well as synaptic strength (O'Sullivan et al., 2014; O'Sullivan et al., 2012).

ADGRL3 therefore plays an important role in the glutamatergic system (Ranaivoson et al., 2015). Importantly, both DA and glutamatergic systems closely interact in the PFC (Tseng and O'Donnell, 2004; Yuen et al., 2013). Independently, glutamate disruption has also been linked to psychiatric disorders including ADHD (Belsham, 2001; Maltezos et al., 2014). Indeed, our leading hypothesis for the pathogenesis of psychotic disorders proposes a

disruption to both these systems emphasizing their interconnected nature and importance to psychiatric disorders (Howes et al., 2015). The link between *Adgrl3* inactivation in the PFC and neuropathology was supported by GSEA and pathway analysis. The enriched KEGG pathways and most overrepresented annotated terms were extremely relevant to nervous system function and dysfunction. Of particular relevance to ADHD is the identification of cocaine and amphetamine addiction pathways. The abnormally expressed genes in the neuroactive ligand pathway (cholinergic receptor, nicotinic, alpha polypeptide 10 SUD (*Chrna10*) and cholinergic receptor, nicotinic, beta polypeptide 10 (*Chrnbl0*)) are also relevant to nicotine addiction (Keskitalo-Vuokko et al., 2011). Individuals with ADHD have markedly increased rates of SUD while polymorphisms in *ADGRL3* in particular have been associated with an increased risk of addiction (Skoglund et al., 2017; Uhl et al., 2008b; Uhl et al., 2008a). The increased risks of nicotine addiction in ADHD individuals may result from a disruption in reinforcement processes caused by alterations in the DA system (Kollins and Adcock, 2014). Indeed, DAT knockout animals also display a dysregulation of nicotinic pathways (Weiss et al., 2007) while animals deficient for the $\beta 2$ -subunit of the nicotinic acetylcholine receptor show the core ADHD features (Granon and Changeux, 2006). The disruption of both DA and addiction associated genes in *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice suggests that this animal model may be useful for further studies into the link between ADHD and addiction.

In contrast to the relatively strong effect of ADGRL3 deficiency on the PFC transcriptome, the number of genes exhibiting significant and large differential expression was very small in the hippocampus (2) and striatum (5). The small degree of differential gene expression seen in the hippocampus is surprising considering that ADGRL3 is known to regulate glutamatergic synapse development in hippocampal neurons (O'Sullivan et al., 2012), while we were also able to detect an impairment in memory domains where the hippocampus plays a critical role. Moreover, since the transcriptomic analysis was performed on adult mouse brains, our subtle hippocampal changes may reflect a reduced relevance of this brain region in adult ADHD in comparison to childhood ADHD (Perlov et al., 2008; Plessen et al., 2006).

The effect of *Adgrl3* depletion on gene expression in the striatum is of particular interest due to the recent finding that *Adgrl3* expression is lower in the striatum of mice bred to be hyperactive in comparison to control mice (Sorokina et al., 2018). Four of the five genes downregulated in the striatum of *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice (*arginine vasopressin*, *oxytocin*, *hypocretin* and *pmch*) are known to directly impact neuronal activity. Two of these genes, *Arginine Vasopressin* and *Oxytocin*, code for neuro-hormones which play a vital role in the regulation of social behaviour and have been commonly linked with ASD, another neurodevelopmental disorder which often appears comorbidly with ADHD (Cataldo et al., 2018; Ghirardi et al., 2018). It seems likely that differential regulation of these genes may contribute to the increased sociability and reduced aggression of *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice. The neurohormones/peptides genes identified are likely to be vital to control both the motor and reward systems. Modulation of the reward system through the striatum is of particular relevance to ADHD (van Hulst et al., 2017). However, these neuro-hormones/peptides are not typically expressed in the mouse striatum. In addition, the previously discussed disruptions to the PFC of *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice may be linked to the differential gene expression seen in the striatum. Striatal dopamine transporter levels have been implicated in the response of individuals with ADHD to MPH; however, unlike in the PFC, dopaminergic gene expression in the striatum does not seem to be directly impacted by the depletion of ADGRL3 (Krause et al., 2005). Differential gene expression in both the PFC and striatum may be linked as dopaminergic modulation is known to regulate striatal neuropeptide levels (Engber et al., 1992). Both *Hypocretin* and *Pmch* code for neuropeptides and were disrupted in the striatum of *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice. The

disruption of neuropeptides may in turn impact dopamine release (Sulzer et al., 2016). Functional connectivity between the PFC and striatum is essential for cognitive and executive processes (Antzoulatos and Miller, 2014). Impairments to this connectivity have previously been linked with psychosis and ASD (Padmanabhan et al., 2013; Simpson et al., 2010). Disruptions to the connections between the PFC and striatum and abnormalities in the dopaminergic system of the PFC can also result in deficits to learning, memory and impulsivity (Puig et al., 2014; Yates et al., 2016). Perturbations to these systems may explain the memory endophenotypes seen in *Adgrl3* knockout mice.

In conclusion, the combination of behavioural and transcriptomic findings further validates constitutive *Adgrl3* knockout mice as an experimental model of ADHD. Gene expression changes in the DA system support the cross-species link between *Adgrl3* inactivation and abnormal function of the DA system while providing an attractive avenue for future pharmacological studies. Identification of significant and biologically relevant gene expression changes, particularly in the PFC and striatum, provides regional targets for future studies involving *ADGRL3* transgenic animals. In addition, future transgenic models created using more specific techniques such as CRISPR-Cas9 may allow creation of disease-associated *ADGRL3* variants which will better answer the question of how specific non-coding polymorphisms in this gene may confer an increased risk of ADHD.

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Author Contributions Statement

NM, AOL, AR, KPL and OR conceived and designed research; NM, TG, AOL, SP, FF, and OR performed research; NM, AOL, SP, FF, AR, MSA, MR, JARQ, KPL, and OR analysed and interpreted data; NM, TG, AOL, SP, FF, AR, MSA, MR, JARQ, KPL and OR wrote the manuscript.

Conflict of interest statement

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Figure Legends

Figure 1. Western blot analysis of mouse brain (prefrontal cortex). **(a)** Lysates show a prominent band of approximately 120 kDa in wildtype (*Adgrl3*^{+/+}) animals, which corresponds to the p120 subunit of ADGRL3 protein. **(b)** Arbitrary fluorescent units were normalized to the internal loading control (tubulin). Data were expressed as percentage of average control values and plotted as relative protein levels. Protein band could not be detected in *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice, whereas significantly reduced levels were observed in heterozygote (*Adgrl3*^{+/-}) mice. Error bars represent Standard Error of the Mean (SEM). Data were analysed by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test; * p≤0.05, ** p≤0.01, *** p≤0.001, **** p≤0.0001.

Figure 2. Light Dark Box: Genotype did not have a significant effect on mouse anxiety levels. **(a)** No significant genotype effect was found on the latency to enter the light section. **(b)** Similarly, no significant genotype effect was found on the amount of time mice spent in the light section. **(c)** A significant genotype effect was found on the total distance travelled by mice, with *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice travelling a significantly greater distance than heterozygous or control mice. Error bars represent SEM. Data were analysed by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test; * p≤0.05, ** p≤0.01, *** p≤0.001, **** p≤0.0001.

Figure 3. Open Field Test: *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice are hyperactive with reduced rearing activity. **(a)** *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice showed markedly reduced rearing activity. **(b)** No significant genotype effect was found on the amount of time mice spent in the central region of the box. **(c)** A significant genotype effect was found on the total distance travelled by mice, with *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice travelling a significantly greater distance than heterozygous or control mice. Error bars represent SEM. Data were analysed by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test; * p≤0.05, ** p≤0.01, *** p≤0.001, **** p≤0.0001.

Figure 4. Gaitlab Analysis: *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice showed differential walking patterns indicative of increased hyperactivity (Stance Time) and possibly unstable footing (Base of Support). **(a) & (b)** *Adgrl3*^{+/+} and *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice did not show a significantly different stride frequency (a) or length (b). **(c)** *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice spent a significantly shorter period of time with their paws on the ground as measured by stance time. In particular the LH paw was found to have a significantly reduced stance time in *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice in comparison to controls. **(d)** The amount of time paws were in the air (Swing time) was not significantly different between genotypes as measured. **(e)** The vertical distance (Gap) between fore and hind limb pairs was not significantly different between genotypes. **(f)** The horizontal cross body distance (Base of Support) was significantly greater in *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice than controls. Abbreviations: LF=Left Fore Limb, RF= Right Fore Limb, LH= Left Hind Limb & RH= Right Hind Limb. Error bars represent SEM. Data were analysed by two-way ANOVA followed by Sidak's multiple comparison test; * p≤0.05, ** p≤0.01, *** p≤0.001, **** p≤0.0001.

Figure 5. Object Recognition Test: *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice displayed reduced object recognition indicative of memory impairment. **(a)** Overall interaction time was unchanged in object recognition (Trial 2) vs object exploration (Trial 1). While no significant genotype effect was detected, a significant trial by genotype interaction was revealed, with *Adgrl3*^{+/+} showing a greater interaction in Trial 2 than Trial 1. **(b)** In the object recognition trial, a significant overall preference for the novel object was detected. No overall genotype effect was detected

but multiple comparison analysis revealed that while *Adgrl3*^{+/+} and +/- mice showed a significant preference for the novel object, *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice did not show any preference. (c) Overall mice showed a significantly reduced distance travelled during the object recognition trial. Multiple comparison analysis revealed this reduction in distance was significant only for *Adgrl3*^{+/+} mice. There was an overall significant genotype effect with *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice travelling a greater distance than *Adgrl3*^{+/+} or +/- mice. Error bars represent SEM. Data were analysed by two-way ANOVA followed by Sidak's multiple comparison test; * p≤0.05, ** p≤0.01, *** p≤0.001, **** p≤0.0001.

Figure 6. Barnes Maze. (a-c) Acquisition Phase: *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice have a deficit in spatial memory resulting in increased escape latency and number of primary errors. (a) *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice have a significantly increased escape latency compared to heterozygous or wild-type mice. (b) *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice showed a significantly increased number of primary errors over wild-type but not heterozygous mice. Heterozygous mice made significantly more errors than wild-type mice. (c) *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice travelled a significantly greater distance than wild-type or heterozygous mice while wild-type mice travelled a greater distance than heterozygous mice. (d-f) Reversal Phase: *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice have increased escape latency during the reversal phase which is also indicative of spatial memory impairment. (d) *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice have a significantly increased escape latency compared to wild-type mice (e) No significant genotype effect was found on the number of primary errors. (f) *Adgrl3*^{-/-} travelled a significantly greater distance than wild-type. Error bars represent SEM. Data were analysed by two-way ANOVA followed by Sidak's multiple comparison test; * p≤0.05, ** p≤0.01, *** p≤0.001, **** p≤0.0001.

Figure 7. Social Interaction Test: *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice showed increased sociability but reduced preference for social novelty. These results are indicative of a social memory impairment. (a) Total interaction time was greater in the social novelty trial with both genotypes showed increased interaction. (b) In the sociability trial, a significant interaction effect was found with *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice showing increased time spent interacting with the mouse cage relative to the empty cage. (c) In the social novelty trial *Adgrl3*^{+/+} mice showed an overall preference for the novel mouse while *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice showed no preference. (d) The total distance travelled in the social novelty trial was significantly less than the sociability trial. While *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice travelled an overall greater distance, there was a significant reduction in their locomotion in the second trial which was not observed in control mice. Error bars represent SEM. Data were analysed by two-way repeated measures ANOVA followed by Sidak's multiple comparison test; * p≤0.05, ** p≤0.01, *** p≤0.001, **** p≤0.0001.

Figure 8. Resident Intruder Test. *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice showed a complete absence of aggression. In comparison to *Adgrl3*^{+/+} mice, *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice had a significantly lower rate of attack. Data were analysed by Fisher exact test; * p≤0.05, ** p≤0.01, *** p≤0.001, **** p≤0.0001.

Figure 9. Continuous performance test (CPT)-Training (a) There were no genotypes difference in the number of sessions to criterion for CPT training stages. (b) *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice showed an increased false alarm rate in comparison to *Adgrl3*^{+/+} mice during the acquisition stage. At baseline performance *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice have an increased reward retrieval latency (t-test: Genotype p=0.0106). (c) At baseline performance *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice have an increased number of inter-trial interval (ITI) touches and reward retrieval latency. All mice were trained for 7 sessions. Error bars represent SEM. Data were analysed by unpaired T- test (b) or two-way ANOVA and t-test (a and c); * p≤0.05, ** p≤0.01, *** p≤0.001, **** p≤0.0001. Asterisks at the top of each panel indicate that mice significantly progressed throughout the

sessions independently of the genotype, whereas asterisks inside the panel refer to global differences between genotypes.

Figure 10. CPT probe trials 1 & 2. *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice showed an increased false alarm rate in Probe 1 (variable stimulus duration) and Probe 2 (variable stimulus contrast) in comparison to *Adgrl3*^{+/+} mice. *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice also showed an increased hit rate in Probe 2 and a decreased response bias (c) in comparison to *Adgrl3*^{+/+} mice. Error bars represent SEM. Data were analysed by two-way ANOVA; * p≤0.05, ** p≤0.01, *** p≤0.001, **** p≤0.0001. Asterisks at the top of each panel indicate that mice significantly progressed throughout the sessions independently of the genotype, whereas asterisks inside the panel refer to global differences between genotypes.

Figure 11. CPT probe trials 3 & 4. *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice showed an increased false alarm rate in Probe 4 (S+ probability) but not in Probe 3 (variable ITI) (Two-way ANOVA, Genotype Probe 4 p=0.0380). No other significant genotype effects were detected. Error bars represent SEM. Data were analysed by two-way ANOVA; * p≤0.05, ** p≤0.01, *** p≤0.001, **** p≤0.0001.

Figure 12. Behaviour Annotated Term. Pathway analysis of differentially expressed genes in the prefrontal cortex of *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice revealed behaviour as the top annotated term. Green genes are downregulated in *Adgrl3*^{-/-} mice while red genes are upregulated. Image made using Ingenuity Pathway Analysis (IPA) software (Qiagen).

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Table 1. Differential Gene Expression Absolute log₂ Fold Change \geq |1|. List of all genes in the prefrontal cortex, hippocampus or striatum which passed the multiple comparison adjusted p-value threshold of 0.05 and had a greater than 50% increase or decrease in expression in the prefrontal cortex, hippocampus or striatum of *Adgrl3* $-/-$ mice.

Table 1	Differential Gene Expression Absolute log ₂ Fold Change \geq 1		
Gene Symbol	Gene Name	log ₂ FoldChange	padj
Prefrontal Cortex			
<i>Slc6a3</i>	<i>solute carrier family 6 (neurotransmitter transporter, dopamine), member 3</i>	-3.030248464	0.000126768
<i>Fermt1</i>	<i>fermitin family member 1</i>	-2.85447429	0.027745238
<i>Barhl2</i>	<i>BarH-like 2 (Drosophila)</i>	-2.341735495	0.012046358
<i>Scgn</i>	<i>secretagogin, EF-hand calcium binding protein</i>	-2.228703229	0.000343187
<i>Chrna10</i>	<i>cholinergic receptor, nicotinic, alpha polypeptide 10</i>	-2.170113334	0.045224968
<i>Chrb4</i>	<i>cholinergic receptor, nicotinic, beta polypeptide 4</i>	-1.975645914	0.028005592
<i>Trh</i>	<i>thyrotropin releasing hormone</i>	-1.895089286	0.000348037
<i>Doc2g</i>	<i>double C2, gamma</i>	-1.868514734	0.020227139
<i>Tbx21</i>	<i>T-box 21</i>	-1.736850578	0.026824467
<i>Cdhr1</i>	<i>cadherin-related family member 1</i>	-1.685605756	0.036880589
<i>Frmd7</i>	<i>FERM domain containing 7</i>	-1.655572263	0.008079282
<i>Th</i>	<i>tyrosine hydroxylase</i>	-1.578888447	0.002841042
<i>Aqp1</i>	<i>aquaporin 1</i>	-1.557704669	0.012046358
<i>Fgf16</i>	<i>fibroblast growth factor 16</i>	-1.428303169	0.028005592
<i>Adamts19</i>	<i>a disintegrin-like and metalloproteinase (reprolysin type) with thrombospondin type 1 motif, 19</i>	-1.303170033	0.030038299
<i>Prss56</i>	<i>protease, serine 56</i>	-1.302985856	0.026824467
<i>Hspb8</i>	<i>heat shock protein 8</i>	-1.188774118	0.002246439
<i>Slc9a4</i>	<i>solute carrier family 9</i>	-1.125190849	0.00157127

	<i>(sodium/hydrogen exchanger), member 4</i>		
<i>Ppef2</i>	<i>protein phosphatase, EF hand calcium-binding domain 2</i>	-1.124102836	0.0318905
<i>Vipr2</i>	<i>vasoactive intestinal peptide receptor 2</i>	-1.097318756	0.01722175
<i>Nmb</i>	<i>neuromedin B</i>	-1.066365486	0.01869699
<i>Il31</i>	<i>interleukin 31</i>	1.85630251	0.012046358
<i>Stbd1</i>	<i>starch binding domain 1</i>	1.969471871	1.41998E-05
Hippocampus			
<i>Plin4</i>	<i>perilipin 4</i>	-1.112291168	0.016872478
<i>Stbd1</i>	<i>starch binding domain 1</i>	1.818306565	5.34443E-07
Striatum			
<i>Shroom3</i>	<i>shroom family member 3</i>	-1.096714321	0.000224201
<i>Stbd1</i>	<i>starch binding domain 1</i>	1.800834865	8.41806E-14
<i>Avp</i>	<i>arginine vasopressin</i>	3.200658475	0.000248666
<i>Oxt</i>	<i>oxytocin</i>	4.034462022	0.000248666
<i>Hcrtr</i>	<i>hypocretin</i>	5.117557719	0.000248666
<i>Pmch</i>	<i>pro-melanin-concentrating hormone</i>	5.370831844	9.32844E-06

Table 2. Prefrontal Cortex Gene Set Enrichment Analysis using Enricher.

Significantly enriched KEGG 2016 Pathways from a list of genes which were more than 50% downregulated in the prefrontal cortex of *Adgrl3* ^{-/-} mice. All five pathways are highly relevant to neurobiology and potentially linked to the neuropathology of ADHD.

Table 2	Prefrontal Cortex Down Regulated Gene Set Enrichment Analysis	
Term	Adjusted P-value	Genes
Cocaine addiction	0.022277215	TH;SLC6A3
Amphetamine addiction	0.022277215	TH;SLC6A3
Neuroactive ligand-receptor interaction	0.022277215	CHRNA10;VIPR2;CHRNA4
Dopaminergic synapse	0.044262629	TH;SLC6A3
Parkinson's disease	0.044262629	TH;SLC6A3

CPT - Probe Trials 1 & 2

Probe 1 - Stimulus duration

Probe 2 - Stimulus contrast

+/+ n=7

-/- n=9

ACCEPTED

Probe 3 - long ITI

Probe 4 - Stimulus probability

ACCEPTED MANUSCRIPT

Object Recognition Test

Barnes Maze

Social Interaction Test

ACCEPTED MA

Highlights

- ▶ ADGRL3 knockout as a model of ADHD
- ▶ Increased activity and reduced aggression in ADGRL3 knockout mice
- ▶ Loss of ADGRL3 impairs learning and memory in mice
- ▶ Region-specific transcriptomic analysis of controls and ADGRL3 knockout mice
- ▶ Strong downregulation of dopamine transporter in the prefrontal cortex of ADGRL3 knockout mice